

OPTIMAL EXCITATION FREQUENCY FOR DELAMINATION IDENTIFICATION OF LAMINATED BEAMS USING A_0 LAMB MODE

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SUMMARY

Numerical investigations on optimal excitation frequency of actuator, which can lead to the strongest reflections from a delamination, have been performed when using A_0 Lamb wave mode. From the results, it can be found that the optimal excitation frequency relates to the natural frequency of a local region containing the delamination.

Keywords: Lamb wave, delamination, laminated beam, excitation frequency

INTRODUCTION

The structural monitoring techniques based on Lamb waves have been explored by many researchers in recent years, and the A_0 mode was validated to be suitable for detecting tiny defects [1-4]. However, the sensitivity of the A_0 mode to defects at different frequencies is different. For enhancing the reliability and robustness of the detecting techniques based on the A_0 mode, the pseudospectral Mindlin plate element proposed by authors [5] is employed to investigate the optimal excitation frequency of actuators, which can result in very strong or even the strongest reflected signals from a delamination in laminated beams. In this paper, to obtain the relationship between the delamination and the excitation frequency, various delamination lengths in cross-ply laminated beams are studied in detail. It is found that there are multiple optimal excitation frequencies for one delamination of a fixed length. Finally, we verify that these multiple optimal excitation frequencies relate to the resonant natural frequencies of a local region containing the delamination.

NUMERICAL ANALYSES METHOD

1. A pseudospectral Mindlin element

In our previous study [5], we have proposed a powerful plate element in the time domain, i.e., pseudospectral Mindlin element. An important advantage of this element is that the numerical errors decrease more quickly than any power of $1/p$, i.e., so-called

Figure 1. A 6x6 spectral plate element

‘spectral convergence’, where p is the order of the used polynomial. The idea of this pseudospectral element method is very similar to that of FEM except for the specific piecewise interpolation functions within elements as it uses.

In this section, we describe the elemental shape functions based on Chebyshev polynomials. The 2D shape functions defined in the local coordinate system of the element as shown in Fig. 1, i.e., $\hat{\Omega} = [-1 \leq \xi \leq 1] \times [-1 \leq \eta \leq 1]$ are described as follows:

$$\Phi_I = \psi_i \psi_j \quad (1)$$

with

$$\psi_i = \frac{2}{N_\xi} \sum_{m=0}^{N_\xi} \frac{1}{c_i c_m} T_m(\xi_i) T_m(\xi) \quad (2a)$$

$$\psi_j = \frac{2}{N_\eta} \sum_{n=0}^{N_\eta} \frac{1}{c_j c_n} T_n(\eta_j) T_n(\eta) \quad (2b)$$

where N_ξ and N_η are the orders of Chebyshev polynomials in ξ and η directions, respectively. Therefore, there are $N_\xi + 1$ nodes in ξ direction and $N_\eta + 1$ nodes in η direction, respectively. And the subscript I in Eq. (1) representing nodal number is

$$1 \leq I \leq (N_\xi + 1)(N_\eta + 1) \quad (3)$$

Also, i, j , and c_i in Eq. (2) are described as

$$0 \leq i \leq N_\xi \quad (4a)$$

$$0 \leq j \leq N_\eta \quad (4b)$$

$$c_i = \begin{cases} 2 & i = 0, N_\xi \text{ or } N_\eta \\ 1 & 0 < i < N_\xi \text{ or } N_\eta \end{cases} \quad (4c)$$

In Eq. (2), T_j are the Chebyshev polynomials of the first kind. They can be expressed as: $T_j(\cos \theta) = \cos(j\theta)$. Using the mapping: $\lambda = \cos \theta$, the Chebyshev polynomials can be written as: $T_j(\lambda) = \cos(j \cos^{-1} \lambda)$.

The grid points to be used for the spectral plate element are the quadrature points of Chebyshev-Gauss-Lobatto quadrature, which are

$$\lambda_i = -\cos\frac{\pi i}{N}, 0 \leq i \leq N_\xi \text{ or } N_\eta \quad (5)$$

where λ_i denotes ξ_i and η_i , respectively, i.e., the local coordinates of grid points.

Taking the 6×6 pseudospectral plate element as an example, there are 6 nodes both in ξ direction and in η direction. It can be seen from Fig. 1 that the distribution of the grid points is irregular which is different from that of conventional FEM whose elemental nodes are uniformly spaced within elements.

In [5], we have shown that an unconventional integration scheme named Chebyshev points quadrature (CPQ), which uses the positions of the grid points as the quadrature points, is very effective to generate the elemental stiffness matrix and the lumped mass matrix. This numerical integration method is based on interpolation, e.g., Lagrange interpolation or Newton's forward interpolation etc. Here, the weight functions of interpolation type quadrature can be obtained from Lagrange interpolation polynomials and described as:

$$W_j = \int_a^b h_j(\lambda) d\lambda, \text{ with } h_j(\lambda) = \frac{\prod_{i \neq j} (\lambda - \lambda_i)}{\prod_{i \neq j} (\lambda_j - \lambda_i)} \quad (6)$$

The integral area of $h_j(\lambda)$ is from $a=-1$ to $b=1$ in Eq. (6). Then, in Eq. (6), λ_i and λ_j are local coordinates of grid points that can be easily calculated from Eq. (5). Therefore, it is easy to get the weight functions of CPQ by using Eq. (6). Usually, the algebraic accuracy of this integration is only of the order of $n-1$ for n integration points, which is lower than that of Gaussian type integration methods, e.g., $2n-1$ for Gauss-Legendre quadrature (GLEQ), and $2n-3$ for Gauss-Lobatto quadrature (GLOQ). However, it is sufficient to integrate a Chebyshev polynomial of the order of $n-1$ when n grid points (or n integration points) are used. We have validated that the accuracy of this integration scheme is very high by using various problems, for example, static and dynamic response analyses, one-dimensional elastic wave propagation problems [5]. The results generated by CPQ are even better than ones obtained by GLEQ. Since the integration points are overlapped with the positions of elemental nodes, the diagonal system mass matrix can be obtained. Therefore, the equations of motion can be easily solved in the time domain by applying the central difference method for reducing the computational cost. Some other aspects for constructing this element are the same with the standard procedures described in various textbooks.

2. Verification of numerical method

Here, to further verify the proposed plate element for 2D plate problems, an aluminum plate of the thickness of 5 mm, which contains a hole of diameter of 2 cm, is employed as shown in Fig. 2. A technique for visualizing ultrasound wave propagation in Ref. [6] is adopted. As shown in Fig. 2, this technique uses a pulsed laser as actuator that scans the test piece for ultrasound wave generation and a fixed acoustic emission (AE) sensor as receiver. The received signals of sensor are stored in a computer by way of an amplifier and a digital oscilloscope. Waveforms are collected at grid points within a given scanning area where the pulsed laser is used to excite ultrasound waves as shown in Fig. 2. By using the assumption of reversible wave propagation, as shown in Fig. 2,

Figure 2. Experimental setup for wave propagation visualization (length unit: mm)

the collected waveform data can be transformed into a set of data which denotes the wave propagation where the sensor works as an actuator and the grid points work as sensors virtually. For details of this technique, one can refer to [6]. Here, in numerical simulations, we use a circular piezoelectric actuator, which is attached at the position of the AE sensor in Fig. 2 on the surface of the plate, to simulate the working condition of the pulsed laser. The diameter and thickness of the virtual piezoelectric actuator is 10 mm and 0.5 mm, respectively. Its material properties are $E=63$ GPa, $G=24.23$ GPa and $d_{31}=210$ pC/N. The excitation signal of the pulsed laser cannot be obtained directly. Here, the response of the AE sensor, which is located very near a point irradiated by the pulsed laser, is used. This experimental signal is shown in Fig. 3. The central frequency of this signal is around 170 KHz. In numerical simulations, the input voltage signal of the piezoelectric actuator is taken from the experimental data before 0.0001s as shown in Fig. 3. The largest element size using CPQ in this analysis is taken as 5 mm, which is smaller than the half wave length of S_0 and A_0 wave modes at 170 KHz. Of course, near the hole, the mesh size is adjusted to be smaller. Both experimental and numerical wave scattering visualizations for A_0 wave mode at $t=71.35 \mu s$ are shown in Fig. 4. From this

Figure 3. Input signal for simulating the excitation force

Figure 4. Comparison of wave propagation results

figure, we can find that the numerical result agrees with the experimental one very well if we compare the transmitted waves and reflected waves near the hole in two figures. This experimental example further validates the effectiveness of our proposed numerical approach for 2D complex problems. Moreover, the computational cost using this new approach is much lower than that of traditional FEM elements.

Next, to verify the effectiveness of the present numerical approach for delaminated laminates, in this research, a CFRP cross-ply laminated composite beam of stack sequence of $[0_{10}/90_{12}/0_{10}]$ is used. The material properties of CFRP are taken as $E_{11}=110$ GPa, $E_{22}=7.04$ GPa, $G_{12}=G_{23}=G_{13}=4.60$ GPa, $\nu_{12}=0.25$, and $\rho=1700$ kg/m³. As shown in Fig. 5, two piezoelectric PZT actuators are attached on the top and bottom surfaces of the beam. The PZT actuator has a width of 10 mm and a thickness of 0.5 mm. The material properties of PZT are the same as stated previously. The out-of-phase voltage of 50 V is applied on two actuators to generate a pure A_0 wave mode. An excitation signal in the following Eq. (7) is adopted to generate A_0 wave mode.

$$P(t) = \begin{cases} 0.5[1 - \cos(2\pi ft / N)]\cos(2\pi ft), & t \leq N / f \\ 0, & t > N / f \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where f is the central frequency in Hz and N is the number of sinusoidal cycles within a pulse.

Two same PZT units are used as sensors to pick up the reflected wave from a delamination. The difference of two signals of two sensors can yield a pure A_0 mode even when there is S_0 mode due to mode change caused by interaction of A_0 mode and the delamination. A comparison of experimental and numerical results at the excitation

Figure 5. Model for a cross-ply delaminated laminated beam

Figure 6. Comparison of numerical and experimental results for a 20 mm delamination

frequency of 50 KHz for a delamination $[0_{10}/90_{12}/0_{10}]$, which is of the length of 20 mm is shown in Fig. 6. These results are normalized by the maximum amplitude of themselves. From this figure, the reflection from the delamination can be clearly identified. Both results agree with each other very well.

NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION FOR DELAMINATED LAMINATES

To obtain the optimal excitation frequency for delaminated laminated beams, a model shown in Fig. 7 is employed. The stacking sequence of laminates is $[0_{10}/90_{12}/0_{10}]$, the same with that in the above section. Two kinds of delamination location along the through-thickness direction are investigated, i.e., $[0/90//90/0]$, $[0//90/90/0]$, respectively. In general, it seems to be a matter of common knowledge: as the excitation frequency increases, the sensitivity of damage detection using ultrasonic waves should be higher since the wave length decreases in this case. To check this point, the wave signals of the beam with a 30mm delamination at the excitation frequencies of 40 KHz and 80 KHz are shown in Fig. 8 for the case of $[0/90//90/0]$. There are three wave packets in the figure. The first wave packet is incident wave, the second is the reflected wave from the delamination and the last one is the reflected wave from the right end of beam. In this figure, there is a strong reflected wave from the delamination at the excitation frequency of 40 KHz, whereas the reflected wave from the delamination is very weak at 80 KHz. This result implies that the above stated common knowledge may be wrong. It is very important to choose the proper excitation frequency. If an inappropriate excitation

Figure 7. Schematic view of a delaminated beam with actuators and sensors (unit: mm)

Figure 8. Wave signals of a beam with a 30mm delamination at the excitation frequencies of 40 KHz and 80 KHz

(a) 10mm~20 mm

(b) 20mm~30 mm

Figure 9. Relationship between excitation frequency and intensity of reflection from delamination (30 mm delamination, [0/90//90/0])

frequency is chosen in delamination detection, a weak reflected wave from a delamination may be generated which would be influenced significantly by noises and be difficult to detect.

To further obtain the relationship between the delamination length and the excitation frequency, extensive numerical analyses on various delamination lengths have been carried out. The intensity of reflections from the delamination is evaluated from the ratio of the amplitude of reflected signal from the delamination and the amplitude of incident wave. The investigated frequency domain ranges from 15 KHz to 120 KHz. When the length of delamination ranges from 10 mm~30 mm, the sensor responses corresponding to various excitation frequencies are shown in Figs. 9(a) and 9(b), respectively for the case of [0/90//90/0]. Note that in longitudinal axis, H0 in Fig. 9 denotes the amplitude of incident wave, and H1 represents the amplitude of the reflected signal from the delamination. From Fig. 9, we can find that there are multiple peaks corresponding to the optimal excitation frequency for one delamination length. The same

Figure 10. Optimal excitation frequency versus delamination length ([0/90//90/0])

Figure 11. Optimal excitation frequency versus delamination length ([0//90/90/0])

situation exists for the delamination case of $[0//90/90/0]$. From Fig. 9, we can pick up these multiple optimal excitation frequencies, which are summarized in Figs 10 and 11 for the cases of $[0/90//90/0]$ and $[0//90/90/0]$, respectively. From these two figures, it can be found that for each peak, its value decreases as the delamination length increases. Also, there are strong discontinuities between several peaks.

To explore this phenomenon more clearly, we analyze the natural frequencies of delaminated region. The upper and lower portions can be analyzed independently. Two kinds of boundary condition are considered, i.e., the fixed and pinned ones. For example, for the case of $[0/90//90/0]$, since the delamination is located at the mid-plane of the laminates, only a half model is enough as shown in Fig. 12(a). However, for the case of $[0//90/90/0]$, the upper and lower portions are analyzed. The vibration modes corresponding to their natural frequencies are plotted in Fig. 13 for $[0/90//90/0]$, where the first, second and third optimal excitation frequencies picked up from Fig. 10 are also shown. From this figure, we can find that the optimal frequencies are very close to some natural frequencies of the delaminated portion. For example, the first optimal excitation frequency is just located between two first natural frequencies of models for two boundary conditions. The second optimal excitation frequency is close to the second natural frequencies. Moreover, the third optimal excitation frequency is close to the seventh natural frequency. The first, second and seventh vibration modes are shown in Fig. 14, which are pure bending mode for A_0 Lamb mode. The third, fourth, fifth and sixth natural frequencies do not relate to the pure bending mode, therefore, they do not have any relationship with our optimal excitation frequency for A_0 Lamb mode even when they may be close to an optimal frequency. There are similar results $[0//90/90/0]$.

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the optimal excitation frequency of A_0 mode has been investigated by

Figure 12. Natural frequency analysis model, a half model for $[0/90//90/0]$

Figure 13. Optimal excitation frequency versus natural frequency

(a) 1st mode (b) 2nd mode (c) 7th mode

Figure 14. Vibration modes of delaminated portion

employing a pseudospectral Mindlin plate element with high accuracy and low computational cost proposed by authors. This method is verified for a metallic plate with a hole and a delaminated beam by using experimental data. Through a large amount of numerical simulations, we have obtained the relationship between the delamination length and the optimal excitation frequency. It is found that there are multiple optimal excitation frequencies even for one delamination length. After analyzing natural frequencies of the delaminated portion in detail, it is found that the optimal excitation frequencies are close to some natural frequencies corresponding to the deformation mode of pure bending, i.e., the deformation mode of A_0 Lamb mode. Therefore, it can be concluded that the strongest reflection from the delamination is caused by resonance of the local delaminated portion determined by its multiple natural frequencies.

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